
ORIGINAL ARTICLE

The Effect of Academic Supervision on the Improvement of the Pedagogic Competence of MAN (Madrasah Aliah Negeri/Indonesia) Jeneponto teachers.

Sirajuddin Saleh¹ | Sri Rahmadani² | Jamaluddin³

^{1,2,3} Universitas Negeri Makassar, Makassar, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT

Supervision is a set of activities carried out by supervisors to assist teachers in developing their abilities, especially in pedagogical abilities. This study aims to determine the effect of academic supervision on increasing the pedagogic competence of MAN (*Madrasah Aliah Negeri/Indonesia*) Jeneponto teachers. This research is a quantitative study with a research population of 70 teachers and the samples in this study were 70 teachers. Data collection techniques used through questionnaires, interviews, and documentation. The data obtained from the research were processed using data analysis consisting of descriptive analysis techniques and inferential statistical analysis. The results showed that the Academic Supervision of MAN Jeneponto was in the very high category with a percentage rate of 85, 77 percent, and for the pedagogical competence of MAN Jeneponto teachers in the very good category with a percentage rate of 85.6 percent which means the level of the relationship was in the very strong category. It can be concluded that there is a positive and significant effect of academic supervision on the pedagogic competence of MAN Jeneponto teachers.

Keywords: Teacher Supervision, Academic, Pedagogical.

INTRODUCTION

Competence is also interpreted as knowledge, skills, and basic values which are reflected in habits of thinking and acting. (Mannayong & Haerul, 2020; Rasyid, 2020; Wicaksono, 2019). In terms of pedagogic, it is the science of education or education, according to which means science that investigates, contemplates the symptoms of educators' actions. The teacher plays an important role in cultural transformation through the school system, especially in managing the interaction of students with learning resources to achieve the desired achievement. (Andriana, Tambe, & Saleh, 2015; Fatmawada, Maswati, & Krismiati, 2020; Suprianto, Arhas, & Salam, 2018). For this reason, teachers must have adequate academic and professional abilities, solid personality

qualities, and live their profession as teachers (Aswinda, Siraj, & Saprin, 2019; Purwandira, Niswaty, & Darwis, 2018). In carrying out the duties of a teacher in a professional manner, many requirements must be possessed by a teacher, among others, academic qualifications, competence, educational certification, physically and mentally healthy.

A teacher must develop pedagogical potential, so the role of the principal is needed to increase the pedagogical potential of teachers (Saleh & Arhas, 2019; Sukmawati, Jamaluddin, Niswaty, & Asmanurhidayani, 2019). National Education Standards, article 28 paragraph 3 point states that what is meant by pedagogic potential is the ability to manage student learning including understanding students, planning and implementing learning, evaluating learning outcomes, and developing students to actualize the variety of potential they have, according to Mulyasa, (2013) at least includes the following aspects, namely: 1). understanding of educational insight or foundation, 2). Understanding of students, 3). Curriculum and syllabus development, 4). Learning design, 5). Implementation of educational and dialogical learning, 6). the use of learning technology, 7). Evaluation of learning outcomes, 8). Development of students to actualize their various potentials.

Supervision is an activity that does not find fault with the teacher but contains more elements of coaching, professional development, and the like so that the condition of the teacher who is being supervised can be identified with deficiencies (Akib & Saleh, 2015; Bustamin, Darwis, & Saleh, 2015; Ncha 2018; Saleh & Arhas, 2019). So that teachers can make improvements to the performance of their duties. To be able to improve teacher performance. Academic supervision by the principal consists of components of supervision planning, implementation of supervision, evaluation of supervision results, and follow-up supervision (Arikunto, 2004).

METHODS

The variables studied in this study were academic supervision as variable X and teacher pedagogic competence variable Y. The research used was associative research. According to (Sugiyono, 2017) associative is the formulation of a research problem that asks between two or more variables. There are three forms of relationship, namely: symmetrical relationships. Causal relationships, and interactive/reciprocal relationships. The relationship contained in this study is causal, meaning that the relationship is causal. So there are independent variables (variables that affect) and dependent (influenced). To measure the variables in this study using a questionnaire instrument (questionnaire) using a Likert scale which is arranged based on the indicator variable population size in this study as many as 70 people. The sample used in this study using a saturated sampling technique. Sampling is saturated (Sugiyono, 2008) is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as the sample. This is often done when the population is relatively small or the study is trying to make generalizations with very few errors. That is the entire population of 70 teachers. And the data collection techniques used in this study consisted of questionnaires, interviews, and documentation.

An activity that is quite important in the entire research process is data processing. By processing the data, it can be seen the meaning of the data that has been collected so that the research results will be immediately known. The data analysis technique in this research is a descriptive statistical analysis technique that aims to determine the description of academic supervision and pedagogical competence of teachers at the MAN Jenepono School. Then the inferential data analysis technique. To determine the normality of data with work facilities (variable X) and employee performance (variable Y) that have been collected, a data normality test is conducted. And a simple linear regression analysis technique that aims to see the effect of academic supervision on increasing teacher pedagogical competence (independent variable X on dependent variable Y).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The data presented in this study are data obtained from the percentage of questionnaires that have been given to 70 people who were the research samples which are intended to determine the description and effect of academic supervision on increasing the pedagogic competence of MAN Jenepono teachers described as follows:

Academic Supervision

Based on data analysis of each item regarding academic supervision, it can be seen from the whole for indicators of learning planning, implementation of learning, evaluation of learning, and follow-up. This can be seen in table 1:

Table 1.

Summary of Data Analysis per Indicator of Academic Supervision Variables.

No	Indicators	N	N	%	Categories
1	Learning Planning	2412	2800	86,14	Very high
2	Implementation of Learning	1790	2100	85,23	Very high
3	Learning Evaluation	1498	1750	85,60	Very high
4	Follow-up	304	350	86,85	Very high
Total		6004	7000	85,77	Very high

Source: Results of SPSS data processing 20

$$\begin{aligned} \% &= \frac{\text{value obtained}}{\text{some items x ideal score x number of respondents}} \times 100 \\ &= \frac{6004}{20 \times 5 \times 70} \times 100 \\ &= \frac{6004}{7000} \times 100 \\ &= 85,77 \% \end{aligned}$$

The summary of the results of the descriptive analysis above shows that the percentage level of MAN Jeneponto's academic supervision is 85.77 in the interval of 0.80 - 1,000 with a very high category.

Teacher Pedagogical Competence.

Based on the analysis of data from each indicator item regarding the understanding of educational insights and foundations, understanding of students, curriculum/syllabus development, learning design, implementation of learning that educates dialogues, utilizing learning technology, evaluating learning outcomes, and developing students to actualize their potential. This can be seen in table 2:

Table 2.

Summary of Data Analysis Results Per Indicator of Teacher Pedagogical Competence Variables

No	Indicators	N	N	%	Categories
1	Understanding of educational insight and foundation	855	700	84	Very good
2	Understanding of students	863	1050	82,19	Very good
3	Curriculum / syllabus development	881	1050	83,90	Very good
4	Learning design	891	1050	84,85	Very good
5	Implementation of learning that educates dialogic	1202	1400	85,85	Very good
6	Utilization of learning technology	301	350	86	Very good
7	Evaluation of learning outcomes	598	700	85,42	Very good
8	development of students to actualize their potential	599	700	85,57	Very good
Total		5992	7000	89.6	Very good

Source: Results of SPSS data processing 20

$$\% = \frac{\text{value obtained}}{\text{number of items} \times \text{ideal score} \times \text{number of respondents}} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{5992}{20 \times 5 \times 70} \times 100$$

$$= \frac{5992}{7000} \times 100$$

$$= 85,6 \%$$

The summary of the results of the descriptive analysis above shows that the percentage level of the pedagogic competence of MAN Jeneponto teachers is 85.6 percent which is in the interval 0.80 - 1,000 with a very good category.

The Effect of Academic Supervision on the Improvement of the Pedagogical Competence of MAN Jeneponto Teachers

The data normality test was carried out to ensure the dependent variable and the independent variable were in the normal category. based on data analysis, the normality test carried out in table 3:

Tabel 3.

Rangkuman Hasil Pengujian Normalitas Data Dengan Sig 5%

Variable	X^2_{count}	X^2_{table}	Df	Categories
Academic supervision	20.657	28.869	18	Normal
Pedagogical competence	24.857	30.143	19	Normal

Source: Results of SPSS data processing 20

Based on the data normality test analysis above in table 3, it is known that the academic supervision variable (X) is declared normally distributed because it has met the price requirements. X^2_h (20.657) smaller (\leq) then X^2_t with df 18 amounting to 28.869. Likewise, the teacher pedagogic competence variable (Y) is normally distributed because it has met the grade requirements X^2_h 24.857 smaller then X^2_t with df 19 amounting to 30.143.

Table 4.

Summary of Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results

ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regressi on	2425.213	1	2425.213	14232.998	.000 ^b
	Residual	11.587	68	.170		
	Total	2436.800	69			

a. Dependent variable pedagogical competence

b. Predictors: (constans). Supervision

From the results of the F-test obtained F_{count} amounting to 14232,9 and F_{table} (3,98) as big as that is meaningful F_{count} bigger than F_{table} . Because $F_{count} > F_{table}$ then H_0 rejected dan H_a accepted. So, directly the results of data processing in this study with the hypothesis that "it is suspected that there is a positive and significant influence of academic supervision on the pedagogic competence of MAN Jeneponto teachers" can be accepted.

Table 5.
The Summary of Product Moment Correlation Testing Results with Sig. 5%

Model Summary ^b										
Mo del	R	R Squar e	Adjuste d Square	Std. Error	Change R	Statistics F	df 1	df 2	Sig. F	
1	.998 ^a	.995	.995	.413	.995	14232.9	1	68	.000	

Source: Results of SPSS data processing 20

a. Predictors: (Constant), supervise

b. Dependent Variable: pedagogical

Based on the results of the correlation analysis of the product-moment research results, it is obtained r_{hitung} amounting to 0,998 then consulted with interpretation guidelines according to (Sugiyono, 2017), so that by looking at the guidelines in table 2 it is written in the correlation coefficient 0.998 which is at the interval 0.80 - 1,000 with a very strong relationship level. Therefore, to test the significance of the relationship found, it applies to the entire population. Is there a significant correlation between the results or not, then it is compared r_{hitung} with r_{tabel} with a significant level of 5 percent and respondent (N) = 70 then r_{tabel} amounting to 0,235

From the results of the product-moment correlation test, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship to academic supervision and pedagogical competence of MAN Jeneponto teachers, because r_{hitung} (0,998) bigger than r_{tabel} (0,235) then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted and it is known that the coefficient of determination is $r^2 = 0.99$ or 99 percent this means that the pedagogic potential of teachers is determined by academic supervision. While the remaining 1% is determined by external factors from academic supervision that have not been studied.

DISCUSSION

Academic Supervision

Academic Supervision is an activity that does not find fault with the teacher, but rather contains elements of coaching, professional development, and the like so that the condition of the teacher being supervised can be identified with deficiencies. So that teachers can make improvements to the performance of their duties. Where the activities

carried out by the teacher are still lacking, it can be strived to be better and can be developed. The results of this study indicate that the level of academic supervision of MAN Jeneponto is in the very high category. This is supported by 4 (four) indicators which include lesson planning, learning implementation, learning evaluation, and follow-up.

The results of this study about the effect of academic supervision on increasing the pedagogic competence of teachers in the Jeneponto MAN school is very important to improve the teaching and learning process of teachers. This research is also in line with the opinion of (Suharsimi, 2013) and explaining that academic supervision by the principal consists of 1. supervision planning, 2. implementation of supervision, 3. evaluation of the results of supervision, and. 4. follow-up

Teacher Pedagogical Competence

Teacher pedagogic potential. Teacher pedagogic potential is the teacher's ability to carry out the learning process properly by mastering all aspects that will be taught to students in-depth and the implementation of educational learning. The results of this study indicate that the pedagogic competence of the MAN Jeneponto teachers is in the very good category. This is supported by 8 (eight) indicators which include: understanding of educational insights or foundations, understanding of students, developing curriculum and syllabus, designing learning, implementing instructional and dialogical learning, utilizing learning technology, evaluating learning outcomes, developing students to actualize their various potentials.

Teacher pedagogic potential in the management of student learning. This must create every teacher to educate the nation's life. The results of the study are in line with the opinion (E. Mulyasa, 2013), at least includes the following aspects, namely: 1). understanding of educational insight or foundation, 2). understanding of students, 3). curriculum and syllabus development, 4). learning design, 5). implementation of educational and dialogical learning, 6). the use of learning technology, 7). evaluation of learning outcomes, 8). development of students to actualize their various potentials.

The Effect of Academic Supervision on the Improvement of the Pedagogic Competency of MAN Jeneponto Teachers.

Based on the results of this study, it can be explained that good academic supervision is carried out by the principal by providing various ways for teachers to increase their potential to be better in the future. A teacher can self-creation by increasing the potential itself.

The results of this study are in line with the opinion (Suhardan, 2010) Supervision can be defined as a supervisor's activity to improve the teaching and learning process. and emphasized that two objectives must be realized by supervision, namely improving teacher professionalism and improving the quality of education so that it can be measured through how teachers can improve pedagogical competence properly. Academic supervision greatly influences the pedagogical potential of teachers where academic supervision is a process of correcting a teacher's mistakes in increasing his / her competence.

CONCLUSION

Based on data analysis and the discussion that describes the effect of academic supervision on increasing the pedagogic competence of MAN Jeneponto teachers, it can be concluded that the description of Academic Supervision (X) at MAN Jeneponto schools is in the very high category, in terms of indicators of learning planning, implementation of learning, evaluation of learning and The teacher pedagogic potential (Y) of the MAN Jeneponto teachers is in the very good category, this is in terms of indicators. understanding of educational insights or foundations, understanding of students, developing curriculum and syllabus learning design, implementing learning that educates and dialogical, utilizing learning technology, evaluating learning outcomes, developing students to actualize their various potentials. From the results of the product-moment correlation test, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship to academic supervision and pedagogical competence of MAN Jeneponto teachers, because r_{count} (0,998) is greater than r_{table} (0.235) then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that there is a very strong influence of academic supervision on the pedagogic competence of MAN Jeneponto teachers.

REFERENCES

- Akib, H., & Saleh, S. (2015). Pengaruh Kepala Sekolah Sebagai Supervisor Terhadap Kinerja Guru Di SMK Negeri 7 Makassar. *Jurnal Office*, 1(2), 141–147.
- Andriana, A., Tambe, M. N., & Saleh, S. (2015). Kompetensi Pedagogik Guru dalam Melaksanakan Proses Pembelajaran di SMK Negeri 1 Makassar. *Jurnal Office*, 1(2), 173–179.
- Arikunto, S. (2004). Dasar-dasar Supervisi. *geografi*.
- Aswinda, A., Siraj, A., & Saprin, S. (2019). Effect of Principal Supervision on Teacher Pedagogic Competencies. *Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Administrasi Publik*, 9(1), 95–100.
- Bustamin, A., Darwis, M., & Saleh, S. (2015). Peran Kepala Sekolah sebagai Supervisor di SMK Negeri 1 Makassar. *Jurnal Office*, 1(2), 166–172.
- E. Mulyasa. (2013). uji kompetensi dan penilaian kinerja guru. In *uji kompetensi dan penilaian kinerja guru*.
- Fatmawada, S., Maswati, R., & Krismiyati, K. (2020). The Effect of Teacher's Pedagogical Competence on Students' Learning Achievement. *PINISI Discretion Review*, 1(1), 155–164.
- Mannayong, J., & Haerul, H. (2020). Analysis of Employee Competency Development at the Corporate Headquarters of Makassar Raya Makassar City Market. *Jurnal Ad'ministrare*, 6(2), 137–144.
- Ncha, G. B. (2018). Existential Justice: The Basis for Quality Leadership. *CAJOLISCalabar Journal of Liberal Studies*, 20(1).
- Purwandira, A., Niswaty, R., & Darwis, M. (2018). Efektivitas Penggunaan Metode

- Pembelajaran Demonstrasi di SMK Negeri 4 Pangkep. *Jurnal Office*, 4(1), 19–24.
- Rasyid, A. R. (2020). Prototype of the Strategy for the Development of HR Competencies in the State Civil Service in Barru Regency. *Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Administrasi Publik*, 10(1), 133–142.
- Saleh, S., & Arhas, S. (2019). The Effect of School Head Academic Supervision on Pedagogic Capability of Basic School Teachers in Manggala District Kota Makassar. *International Conference on Social Science 2019 (ICSS 2019)*. Atlantis Press.
- Sugiyono. (2008). Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D. In *Alfabeta*. <https://doi.org/2008>
- Sugiyono. (2017). *Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, Kombinasi, R&D dan Penelitian Evaluasi*. Bandung: Alfa Beta.
- Suhardan, D. (2010). Supervisi Profesional Layanan Untuk Meningkatkan Mutu Pembelajaran. *Kantor Pengacara dan Konsultan Hukum "Prof. Oemar seno Adji dan Rekan" Jakarta 2002*.
- Suharsimi, A. (2013). Dasar-Dasar Evaluasi Pendidikan. *Jakarta: Bumi Aksara*.
- Sukmawati, S., Jamaluddin, J., Niswaty, R., & Asmanurhidayani, A. (2019). The Influence of Headmaster Leadership Style on Teacher Performance. *Jurnal Office*, 4(2), 91–102.
- Suprianto, S., Arhas, S. H., & Salam, R. (2018). Pengaruh Media Pembelajaran dan Pengelolaan Kelas terhadap Prestasi Belajar Siswa di SMK Negeri Kecamatan Tanete Riattang, Kabupaten Bone. *Jurnal Ad'ministrare*, 5(2), 137–146.
- Wicaksono, W. (2019). Influence of Competence and Customer Service Motivation on the Performance of the Bank Syariah Mandiri Remittance Business Unit. *PINISI Discretion Review*, 3(1), 93–102.